

Abstract

31

32 Rapid active stretching the muscle induced a peak passive tension. The muscle was
33 tolerated an isometric static stretch after the active stretch, and presented a subsequent
34 relaxation phase with the passive tension attenuation. A myogenic spontaneous
35 contraction may generated in this phase. The spontaneous contraction relative force
36 enhancement may interrupt the relaxation process in cardiac muscle. In this study, we
37 investigated the spontaneous contraction occurrence and its force enhancement
38 properties in relaxation phase of excessive stretched cardiac muscle. The cardiac
39 papillary muscle was isolated from the *Kunming* mice cardiac ventricle, primarily
40 stabled in *Ringer's* solution. The preparations were lengthening to 20% of its initial
41 length to obtain a low preload. A single active stretch carried out under this low
42 preload. The preparation further lengthening to 40% of its low preload length to be in
43 a high preload condition. Muscle was continuously excessively active stretched twice
44 under the high preload condition. The excessive static stretch induced spontaneous
45 force amplitude (A_{IFE}), force enhancement extensive time in 1st and 2nd stretch (t_1 and
46 t_2) and velocity increases % of time in 2nd stretch were analysed. The results indicated
47 that a significant spontaneous force arose under the high preload condition. However,
48 the amplitude and extensive duration were depending on the strengthening of
49 excessive load. 1) Muscle force enhancement time (t_2) was significantly prolonged
50 because of bearing the 2nd excessive load under high preload condition, however the
51 Ca^{2+} concentration not significantly affect t_2 . The t_2 prolongation existed both in
52 intact muscles and shed muscles (117.42±34.80 msec and 260.20±34.50 msec). 2) The
53 spontaneous force amplitude (A_{IFE}) in 2nd excessive load surpassed its passive tension
54 maximum (PT_{max}) in Ca^{2+} rich solutions (6327.49±524.52 mg to 4576.96±435.80 mg,
55 2062.10±287.59 mg to 1132.13±98.25 mg, in *Ringer's* solution and 3%
56 $CaCl_2$ -modified *Ringer's* solution respectively), however, no surpass observed in Ca^{2+}
57 lacking solutions and in *CfTX-1* shed muscle (1121.76±320.25 mg to 1868.87±119.59
58 mg respectively). 3) In 2nd excessive load, force enhancement maximum tension–time
59 integral (TTI_{max}) was not depending on Ca^{2+} concentration, however the force
60 enhancement velocity maximum (dT/dt_{max}) was significant increasing in high Ca^{2+}

61 solution and shed preparations. We concluded that the excessive load facilitated the
62 force enhancement generation during cardiac muscle relaxation. The significant
63 myogenic spontaneous contraction relative force enhancement interrupted the cardiac
64 muscle relaxation process, prolonged cardiac diastolic phase. *CfTX-1* peptide was the
65 compound prolonged the cardiac muscle relaxation process by reducing the A_{IFE} and
66 extending the t . This study is useful from further developing the study of the
67 contraction-relaxation cycle interruption in overload heart.

68 **Key word:** cardiac papillary muscle; mechanical stretch; myogenic spontaneous
69 contraction; *CfTX-1* peptide

70

71 **Introduction**

72 Longitude lengthening the muscle is the method to mimic the preload conditions and
73 investigating stretch induced rapid increasing of muscle tone and the subsequently
74 attenuating of the passive tension. When instantaneous stretch the muscle excessively
75 that was stretched beyond of its optimum length, a significant myogenic spontaneous
76 contraction may occurred that induced force enhancement in relaxation phase^[1]. This
77 spontaneous contraction waveform was so-called the discrepancy of muscle force^[2],
78 or residual force enhancement. The earlier findings of the spontaneous contraction
79 induced force enhancement (EF) was from the *in vitro* muscle preparation of skinned
80 muscle fibres^[3] and the intact muscle strips^[4, 5]. In intact muscle preparation, this
81 myogenic spontaneous contraction occurrence was primarily considered as the
82 response to its sarcomere rearrangement and elastic properties^[7]. The further studies
83 of spontaneous contraction indicated that the occurrence mechanism was due to the
84 differences of sarcomere length during muscle bundle elongation^[12], or increased
85 recruitment of myosin heads^[13], or shortening length reducing passive tension^[14].
86 Ca^{2+} was another aspect of the occurrence which was considered from the
87 concentrated Ca^{2+} bonding in myofilaments^[6], the altered calcium sensitivity in
88 sarcomeric myofilaments^[15], the lowered cytosolic Ca^{2+} concentration during muscle
89 relaxation^[16], or the sustained without attenuation of the Ca^{2+} binding to myosin-actin
90 sites^[17]. The spontaneous contraction and its EF probably was the important event in

91 relaxed cardiac muscle. However, the role of EF in high preload cardiac muscle, and
92 its physiological significance is not clear.

93 Myogenic spontaneous contraction and FE probably occur in the heart during diastole.
94 This hypothesis is based on the fact that heart chambers regularly tolerated excessive
95 preload in its relaxation period. In the conventional view of diastole, cardiac muscle
96 relaxation was regarded as a mere passive process and an essential step in the blood
97 pumping cycle [8]. However, cardiac muscle bore a significant transient excessive load
98 in the late diastolic phase. The “kick from atrium” that was one kind of transient extra
99 pressure from the atria, act on relaxing ventricular muscle [9], became a transient
100 excessive load in ventricle diastole. As shown in **Figure 1A**, an initially excessive
101 load within ventricle was from a transient atrial pressure increasing (the dot curve
102 from ① to ②, * was the transient atrial pressure maximum, ② was atrial equivalent
103 pressure point to the moment diastole pressure in ventricle). In **Figure 1B**, the atrial
104 pressure excessive load decelerated ventricle relaxation velocity at late diastole phase
105 (duration of the curve marked with **a** and **b**, compared with the duration of the curve
106 marked with **a'** and **b'**). When the excessive load was extremely high, end diastolic
107 process may interrupted by the occurred significant force enhancement. An example
108 of concerned was the interrupted end diastolic pressure in heart failure people who
109 were with normal ejection fraction. In this type patients, exercise induced an abnormal
110 increasing of end diastolic pressure [10]. This specific end diastolic pressure increasing
111 pertain to the decompensating of cardiac muscle relaxation. In clinic diagnosis, the
112 end diastole pressure gradually becomes the basis for judging heart dysfunction [11],
113 therefore spontaneous contraction and FE occurrence in relaxed cardiac muscle
114 probably can be an *in vitro* index to evaluate cardiac muscle compensatory capacity.

115

116 **Figure 1 Here**

117 The membrane permeability may also involve in spontaneous contraction and FE
118 occurrence in excessive preload cardiac muscle. Increased influx of L-type Ca^{2+}
119 current and sarcolemma calcium activated by pore-forming toxin *Sp-CTx* can
120 accelerate the first temporal derivative of the isometric contraction (dP/dt) [18].

121 *CfTX-1* contributed to intracellular Ca^{2+} release, improving cAMP and PKA activity
122 in cardiomyocytes [19], enhancing membrane polarization in urothelium [20], however
123 its cytotoxic potency was lower than that of other venoms and presents with fewer
124 cardiotoxic effects *in vitro* [21]. *CfTX-1* affected muscle excitation-contraction was
125 based on its structural homology with three-domain Cry toxins (δ -endotoxins) and the
126 α -helices of the N-terminal domain [22, 23]. Its specific lipid-dependent cell penetration
127 induces a transient membrane leakage for cardiomyocyte interaction at the atomic
128 level [24], involved in isometric force [25]. In this study, we established an active stretch
129 method to observe the spontaneous contraction and FE occurrence during muscle
130 tolerance the sustained static stretch. We hypothesis that the spontaneous contraction
131 and RFE occurrence is a significant physiological event in excessive preload cardiac
132 muscle. This event interrupt relaxation process in cardiac muscle preparation.

133

134 **Materials and Methods**

135 *Mice cardiac papillary muscle preparation*

136 The animal experiment protocol was approved by the Laboratory Animal Centre,
137 Hainan Medical College, under the guidelines of the Institutional Animal Care and
138 Use Committee (8th Edition, International Standard Book Number-13:
139 978-0-309-15401-7). The papillary muscles were isolated from cardiac ventricle of
140 male *Kunming* mice (n=10, 4 weeks, SPF grade) and prepared in *Ringer's* solution.
141 The preparations were ligatured its end with artificial suture (United States
142 Pharmacopeia Convention designation 7-0), then horizontally placed on a 4°C chilled
143 glass slide surface and immersion in *Ringer's* solution. The muscle bundle one side
144 was fixed on a micro stepping tuner, the other side was hooked on the reed of
145 Wheatstone bridge-type piezoelectric strain sensor (Model JH-2 10g, Beijing
146 Aerospace Medical Engineering Institute, Beijing China). Tuning the micrometre
147 (SV-4 series, Chengdu TME Technology Co, Ltd, Chengdu, China) to obtain 1 g
148 initial preload on muscle which was defined as the optimal length (L_0).

149 For preparing the intact muscle, the isolated papillary muscles were incubated in 4°C
150 *Ringer's* solution during the whole stretching procedure; the shed muscles were

151 prepared in 35 mmol *CfTX-1* peptide solution for 10min and kept in 4°C *Ringer's*
152 solution for further use. All the preparations were loaded 1 gram to obtain its own
153 initial length before operating the active stretch.

154

155 *The procedure of muscle mechanical stretch*

156 The procedure for stretch the muscle preparations were shown in **Figure 2**. After 5
157 min stable at its initial length in 4°C *Ringer's* solution, the muscle was slowly
158 extended 20% of its initial length by tuning the micrometre. This defined as low
159 preload condition. The muscle was rapidly active stretched once under this low
160 preload condition (0.5 mm lengthening, marked AS in **Figure 2**). The muscle
161 tolerated static stretch after the active stretch (the dotted arrow mark behind AS in
162 **Figure 2**). On the myograph, an initial amplitude rising of passive tension and
163 subsequently passive tension attenuation curve was recorded. The FE normally
164 generated in this attenuated phase. After testing under the low preload condition, the
165 muscle further lengthened 40% of its low preload length to obtain a high preload
166 condition. The muscle obtained twice active stretch under this high preload condition
167 (1st and 2nd AS in **Figure 2**, 0.5mm for each stretch). The muscle tolerated excessive
168 mechanical load after the 1st and 2nd active stretch respectively (the dotted arrow after
169 1st and 2nd AS in **Figure 2**)

170 The intact muscle preparation was stretched in the *Ringer's* solution, Ca²⁺ modified
171 *Ringer's* solution (3% CaCl₂ included), *Nifedipine* (1.5 mmol/L), or 0.9% saline
172 solution respectively. The *CfTX-1* peptide shed muscle preparation was operated in
173 *Ringer's* solution only.

174

175 **Figure 2 here**

176

177 *The myograph of passive tension and subsequent FE*

178 The passive tension and myogenic spontaneous contraction during relaxation were
179 recorded by BL-420S Data Acquisition & Analysis System (Chengdu TME
180 Technology Co, Ltd, Chengdu, China). The FE amplitude (**A_{IFE}**) and duration of FE

181 from its peak (t), value of the passive tension maximum (PT_{max}) was directly
182 measured from the recorded myograph; the maximum tension–time integral (TTI_{max})
183 and the maximum rate of force enhancement increase (dT/dt_{max}) were calculated by
184 using TM_WAVE software (Chengdu Techman Software Co., Ltd, Chengdu, China).

185

186 *Statistical analysis*

187 The passive tension and FE values were presented as means \pm SEMs. The value
188 differences under the preload conditions were analysed by using unpaired t -test
189 method (Excel 2013, 2012 Microsoft Corporation). $p < 0.001$ indicated a significant
190 difference.

191

192 **Results:**

193 *Passive tension and the FE in intact muscles under different preload*

194 Under the low preload condition in *Ringer's* solution:

195 The passive tension curve as presented in **Figure 3A**. Rapid single active stretch
196 created a maximum passive tension (I, PT_{max} marked with *, 1213.70 ± 147.38 mg),
197 while a subsequently passive tension attenuation generated (marked with II, dotted
198 line with arrow in **Figure 3A**) where the muscle continuously tolerated the sustained
199 static stretch. In attenuation phase (II), a slight myogenic spontaneous contraction
200 occurred during muscle relaxation to form a secondary spike (3 in figure, A_{IFE} was
201 the maximum value of FE), however the A_{IFE} did not surpass its PT_{max} . Under the
202 low preload condition, single stretched A_{IFE} , TTI_{max} and dT/dt_{max} was
203 1132.35 ± 161.91 mg, 20.46 ± 4.81 g·sec, 3.76 ± 0.52 g/sec respectively. The FE time (t)
204 was 112.47 ± 21.20 msec, therefore the total attenuation (II) was extended to
205 123.72 ± 31.58 msec. t dominated approximately 90% of the total phase II.

206 Under the high preload condition in *Ringer's* solution:

207 As presented in **Figure 3B**, the FE amplitude (A_{IFE} in 1st and 2nd stretch) and FE
208 extended time (t_1 and t_2) in high preload condition were various by stretches. A_{IFE}
209 in 2nd stretch as significantly increased to surpass its PT_{max} . t_2 was significantly
210 extended than the t_1 .

211

212 **Figure 3 here**

213

214 Under the high preload condition in 3% CaCl₂ modified *Ringer's* solution, *Nifedipine*
215 intervention or 0.9% *saline* solution:

216 The intact muscle passive tension waveform in the Ca²⁺ modified *Ringer's* solution
217 under the high preload condition was presented in **Figure 4A**. **A_{IFE}** in 2nd stretch
218 significantly surpassed its **PT_{max}**. However, *Nifedipine* intervention reduced the **A_{IFE}**
219 in both stretches, **A_{IFE}** did not surpass its **PT_{max}**. **A_{IFE}** and **PT_{max}** in *Nifedipine*
220 intervention intact muscle was 909.75±11.91 mg, 1779.66±157.71 mg respectively. In
221 0.9% *saline* solution (Ca²⁺ absent), **A_{IFE}** in 2nd stretch did not surpassed its **PT_{max}**
222 (**Table 1**). The results suggested that Ca²⁺-channel activation and extra Ca²⁺ involved
223 in myogenic spontaneous contraction and the **A_{IFE}**.

224

225 **Figure 4 here**

226

227 The intact muscle FE time in 1st stretch (**t₁**) was significantly shorter than the time (**t**)
228 under low preload condition (**t₁** was 60% short of **t**). The FE time in 2st stretch (**t₂**)
229 was 117.42±34.80 msec (156% extended than **t₁**), as well as the **t₂** and **t₁** was
230 extended in Ca²⁺-modified *Ringer's* solution (**Table 1**). In *Nifedipine* intervention
231 preparations **t₂** and **t₁** was not significantly extended (71.47±9.39 msec and
232 66.74±5.83 msec, respectively, the original waveform was in **Figure 4B**). This result
233 suggested that inactivated Ca²⁺-channel was effectiveness in reducing FE time
234 interrupted relaxation process in excessive load muscle. However, in 0.9% *saline*
235 solution (Ca²⁺ absent), **t₂** and **t₁** in 0.9% *saline* solution were 103.48±8.80 msec and
236 61.86±3.36 msec respectively, 129% extended than **t₁**, the original waveform was in
237 **Figure 4C**). The above results indicated that FE time depended on strengthen of
238 excessive load, as well determined by Ca²⁺-channel activation.

239 In *Ringer's* solution, the intact muscle **TTI_{max}** was 64.32±9.74 g·sec and 38.01±4.38
240 g·sec in 2nd and 1st stretch respectively (comparing a marked dotted columns in

241 **Figure 5A**, *** means $p < 0.001$), while in CaCl_2 modified *Ringer's* solution, TTI_{max}
242 was reduced in 2nd stretch (comparing **b** marked white columns in **Figure 5A**, ***
243 means $p < 0.001$). However, in *Nifedipine* intervention *Ringer's* solution, TTI_{max}
244 significantly increased in 2nd stretch (comparing **c** marked grey columns in **Figure 5A**,
245 *** means $p < 0.001$). The results come to the conclusion that TTI_{max} was an
246 excessive load strengthen index, it was not exactly depending on the extracellular
247 Ca^{2+} concentration.

248 In *Ringer's* solution, the intact muscle $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ was 5.21 ± 0.39 g/sec and 4.58 ± 0.61
249 g/sec in 2nd and 1st stretch respectively (dotted columns in **Figure 5B**). In CaCl_2
250 modified *Ringer's* solution, $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ was significantly increased in 2nd stretch
251 (comparing **b** marked white columns in **Figure 5B**, *** means $p < 0.001$). However, in
252 *Nifedipine* intervention *Ringer's* solution, $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ was reduced in 2nd stretch without
253 statistic significant difference. The results suggested that $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ was sensitive to
254 excessive load, as well depending on Ca^{2+} -channel activation.

255 The results of PT_{max} , A_{IFE} , and **t** in each stretch was summarized in **Table 1**.

256

257 **Table 1 here**

258

259 *Passive tension and FE in CfTX-1 peptide shed muscles under high preload condition*

260 In *Ringer's* solution, shed cardiac muscle A_{IFE} values did not significantly surpassed
261 its PT_{max} (1150.60 ± 90.12 mg and 1868.87 ± 119.59 mg in 2nd stretch, 1150.60 ± 90.12
262 mg and 1066.49 ± 101.33 mg in 1st stretch respectively, the original myograph was
263 presented in **Figure 4D**). However, t_2 was significantly extended than its t_1
264 (260.20 ± 34.50 msec and 190.29 ± 23.10 msec respectively, t_2 was 137% extended to t_1).
265 These results demonstrated that shed muscle A_{IFE} was reduced in bearing excessive
266 load. However the FE time (t_2) was significantly extended, therefore prolonged the
267 total relaxing time.

268 TTI_{max} were 70.20 ± 8.50 g*sec and 43.90 ± 5.20 g*sec in 2nd and 1st stretch
269 respectively (black columns in **Figure 5A**, the slight increasing in 2nd stretch but no

270 statistic significant difference). dT/dt_{max} were 105.50 ± 17.40 g/sec and 59.60 ± 7.30
271 g/sec in 2nd and 1st stretch respectively (comparing **d** marked black columns in **Figure**
272 **5B**, *** means $p < 0.001$). The results indicated that shed muscle dT/dt_{max} was
273 sensitive to strengthen of the excessive load. *CfTX-1* peptide increased the
274 spontaneous contraction dT/dt_{max} in relaxed cardiac muscle.

275

276 **Figure 5 here**

277

278 *A briefing of synthesized CfTX-1 peptide in this study*

279 The *CfTX-1* peptide sequence was identified from the crude venom of the *Aurelia*
280 *aurita* tentacles (*A. aurita*, captured in the northern coast of Hainan Province, China),
281 then laboratory synthesized and purified.

282 In brief, frozen tentacles from *A. aurita* were placed in an autolysis solution, which
283 was then centrifuged at $20,000 \times g$ for 1 h at $4^{\circ}C$. The derived resultant supernatant
284 was immediately frozen at $-80^{\circ}C$ in a condenser chamber and vacuum to extreme
285 dryness (VirTis Bench Top freeze dryer, SP industries, Inc., PA, U.S.A.).
286 Lyophilized cVN was stored at $-20^{\circ}C$ for further SDS-PAGE analysis. The *CfTX-1*
287 peptide sequence was identified from the 43 kDa band in 10% polyacrylamide gel
288 (**Figure 6A**; SD lane: protein molecular marker, cVn lane: *A. aurita* crude venom; 43
289 kDa was the expected band in the cVn lane). The identified *CfTX-1* peptide was 11
290 amino acids that had a high overlap with the positive strain of amino acid sequences
291 304–314 (*IFNFFDLmKVK*) of full length of *CfTX-1* (UniProtKB-A7L035). This
292 *CfTX-1* 11 amino acids were further synthesized by using a commercial resin
293 solid-phase method, then finally lyophilized and quality control analysed by HPLC
294 and Electrospray Ionization Tandem Mass Spectrometry (ESI-MS). The peak intensity
295 value of 1027 at 1400 Da represented the purified synthesized product of the *CfTX-1*
296 peptide (**Figure 6B**).

297

298 **Figure 6 here**

299

300 **Discussion:**

301 In this study we testified that the spontaneous contraction and relative force
302 enhancement occurrence in relaxing cardiac muscle under the high preload condition.

303 In excessive load tolerance cardiac muscle, the significant increased FE amplitude
304 (A_{IFE} in 2nd stretch) and its time (t_2) was the important event, interrupted the cardiac

305 muscle relaxation process. In 1950s, Abbott et al. mentioned an excess of tension
306 generation appreciably greater than the tension developed in isometric contraction in

307 the rapid stretched toad sartorius preparation (1.9 mm/sec) [26]; Hill et al. reported the
308 enhanced tension in well-developed toad sartorii in the stretch-lengthened contractile

309 component [27]. After 20 years, Sugi indicated the tetanic stimulated muscle tension
310 beginning to rise again to the initial isometric value in stretched frog semitendinosus

311 [28]. All of these earlier results reported force enhancement was the increasing of
312 myogenic spontaneous force amplitude. Our results first time to reported that the

313 force enhancement was included the significant time extension in excessive load
314 cardiac muscle. Herzog et al. verified the residue force was from the correct

315 alignment of the muscle filaments that was in the overlap zones in tetanus muscle
316 fibres [29], who related force enhancement to myofilament sliding mechanism. After

317 that force enhancement was demonstrated from the sarcomere length non-uniformities,
318 cross-bridge action, and passive structural elements [30]. Edman was aware of the

319 residual force enhancement from the non-uniform distribution of the myofilament
320 during the length change [31], enhancement occurred on the ascending portion of the

321 force-length relationship [32]. In our muscle stretching experiment model, the high
322 preload condition was the situation of the cardiac muscle that bearing the excessive

323 static stretch load beyond optimal length. Our new evidences from the results
324 indicated that the augmentation of force enhancement waveform was not only the

325 A_{IFE} surpassing of its PT_{max} , but also the significant extended time (t) during cardiac
326 muscle relaxation. Under the high preload condition, this excessive load augmentation

327 was basically relative to strengthen of the static stretch and Ca^{2+} concentration.

328 In addition, the force enhancement in cardiac muscle also included the myogenic
329 spontaneous contraction TTI_{max} and dT/dt_{max} increasing. However, these time relative

330 index increasing varies according to strengthen of the excessive load sand the Ca^{2+}
331 environment.

332 The intact muscle TTI_{max} was significant depend on strengthen of excessive load. The
333 TTI_{max} was increased in 2nd stretch than in 1st stretch either in *Ringer's* solution or in
334 *Nifedipine* intervened *Ringer's* solution. High concentration of Ca^{2+} and *CfTX-1*
335 peptide did not help for this increasing. TTI_{max} was the index for evaluating the time
336 dependence of the muscle tension. This index was used for determining the muscle
337 energy output in its isometric contractions [33]. In striated muscle, this parameter used
338 to determining the capacity ratio of the diaphragm [34], analysing the transient
339 contraction [35], and evaluating the effects of contractile filament mutations on muscle
340 twitch [36]. Cardiac muscle TTI_{max} was the index for determining the ventricular
341 muscle onset of contractions in diastole-systolic cycle [37, 38]. In our muscle stretching
342 study, TTI_{max} was the myogenic spontaneous contraction index. In excessive load
343 intact cardiac muscle, an increased TTI_{max} was relative to the shortening of
344 spontaneous contraction time (t_2), therefore indicated less interruption of the
345 relaxation process (such as in *Nifedipine* intervened preparation).

346 $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ was the unique parameter for evaluating the right heart systolic function [39],
347 investigating the antagonists facilitate the peak rate of cardiac muscle tension
348 development [40]. Tamiya et. al. demonstrated the relationship between $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ and
349 muscle inotropes [41], characterized $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ as the isometric relaxation index. In our
350 experiment, myogenic spontaneous contraction $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ presented as the sensitive
351 index to strengthen of excessive load. The $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ in 2nd stretch were largely
352 increased both in intact muscle and *CfTX-1* peptide shed muscle. However the
353 $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ increasing in 2nd stretch was substantially suppressed by *Nifedipine* (the
354 comparing the grey bars in **Fig 5B**). This result suggested that $\text{dT/dt}_{\text{max}}$ increasing in
355 excessive load cardiac muscle was depending on the activation of Ca^{2+} -channel.

356 The experiment indicated *CfTX-1* peptide was the effective compound to reduce
357 myogenic spontaneous contraction A_{IFE} and prolonged t in excessive cardiac muscle.
358 The biological utility of *CfTX-1* peptide was balancing the passive tension peak and
359 the relaxation process in excessive load cardiac muscle. This effect will help to play a

360 role in the study of compensation in overload myocardium in the future.
361 Finally, we concluded that the myogenic spontaneous contraction relative
362 augmentation of force enhancement was the multiple event. Under the high preload
363 condition, the excessive load induced significant augmentation of force enhancement
364 prolonged the relaxation time, therefore interrupted the cardiac muscle regular
365 relaxation process. This force enhancement probably frequently occurred in the heart
366 late diastole phase during muscle tolerance pressure or volume overload, and
367 disrupted the regular cardiac cycle.

368

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372

373 **Conflicts:**

374 The authors do not have any conflicts of interest.

375

376 **Authors' contributions**

377 Yang Wang, Min Yin, Han Wang and Annie Christel Bell, and Shouyan Fan carried
378 out the study design, membrane preparations, venom preparations and identification,
379 and participated in the draft of the manuscript and the primary revision.

380 Joseph Akparibila Azure, Mohammad Alshorman, and Abhay Pratap Singh prepared
381 the mouse cardiac papillary muscle strips and performed the stretching analysis.

382 Zhibin Chen and Lingfeng Gao participated in the reference search and the design of
383 the study, performed the statistical analysis and helped draft the manuscript.

384 All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

385

386 **References:**

387 1. Edman, K.A., & Flitney, F.W. Non-uniform behaviour of sarcomeres during
388 isometric relaxation of skeletal muscle. *J. Physiol.* **276**, 78-79 (1978).

389 2. Noble, M.I. Enhancement of mechanical performance of striated muscle by stretch

- 390 during contraction. *Exp. Physiol.* **77**(4), 539-552 (1992).
- 391 3. Fukutani, A., Joumaa, V., & Herzog, W. Influence of residual force enhancement
392 and elongation of attached cross-bridges on stretch-shortening cycle in skinned
393 muscle fibers. <https://doi.org/10.14814/phy2.13477> (2017).
- 394 4. Fortuna, R., Power, G.A., Mende, E., Seiberl, W., & Herzog, W. Residual force
395 enhancement following shortening is speed-dependent. *Sci. Rep.* **12**, 5:21513 (2016).
- 396 5. Hahn, D., & Riedel, T.N. Residual force enhancement contributes to increased
397 performance during stretch-shortening cycles of human plantar flexor muscles *in vivo*.
398 *J. Biomech.* **22**(77), 190-193 (2018).
- 399 6. Edman, K.A.P., & Caputo C. Release of calcium into the myofibrillar space in
400 response to active shortening of striated muscle. *Acta. Physiol.* **221**(2), 142-148
401 (2017).
- 402 7. Kulke, M., Fujita-Becker, S., Rostkova, E., Neagoe, C., Labeit, D., Manstein, D.J.,
403 Gautel, M., & Linke, W.A. Interaction between PEVK-titin and actin filaments: origin
404 of a viscous force component in cardiac myofibrils. *Circ. Res.* **89**(10), 874-881
405 (2001).
- 406 8. Biesiadecki, B.J., Davis, J.P., Ziolo, M.T., Janssen, P.M.L. Tri-modal regulation of
407 cardiac muscle relaxation; intracellular calcium decline, thin filament deactivation,
408 and cross-bridge cycling kinetics. *Biophys. Rev.* **6**(3-4), 273-289 (2014).
- 409 9. Leite-Moreira, A.F. Current perspectives in diastolic dysfunction and diastolic heart
410 failure. *Heart.* **92**(5), 712-718 (2006).
- 411 10. Westermann, D., Kasner, M., Steendijk, P., Spillmann, F., Riad, A., Weitmann, K.,
412 Hoffmann, W., Polle r, W., Pauschinger, M., Schultheiss, H.P., & Tschöpe, C. Role of
413 left ventricular stiffness in heart failure with normal ejection fraction. *Circulation.*
414 **117**(16), 2051-2060 (2008).
- 415 11. Xi, J., Lamata, P., Niederer, S., Land, S., Shi, W., Zhuang, X., Ourselin, S., Duckett,
416 S.G., Shetty, A.K., Rinaldi, C.A., Rueckert, D., Razavi, R., & Smith, N.P. The
417 estimation of patient-specific cardiac diastolic functions from clinical measurements.
418 *Med. Image Anal.* **17**(2), 133-146 (2013).
- 419 12. Rain, S., Handoko, M.L., Trip, P., Gan, C.T., Westerhof, N., Stienen, G.J., Paulus,

420 W.J., Ottenheijm, C.A., Marcus, J.T., Dorfmüller, P., Guignabert, C., Humbert, M.,
421 Macdonald, P., Dos Remedios, C., Postmus, P.E., Saripalli, C., Hidalgo, C.G., Granzier,
422 H.L., Vonk-Noordegraaf, A., van der Velden, J., & de Man, F.S. Right ventricular
423 diastolic impairment in patients with pulmonary arterial hypertension. *Circulation*.
424 **128**(18), 2016-2025, 1-10 (2013).

425 13. Campbell, K.S., Janssen, P.M.L., & Campbell, S.G. Force-dependent recruitment
426 from the myosin off state contributes to length-dependent activation. *Biophys. J.*
427 **115**(3), 543-553 (2018).

428 14. Brown, L.M., & Hill, L. Some observations on variations in filament overlap in
429 tetanized muscle fibres and fibres stretched during a tetanus, detected in the electron
430 microscope after rapid fixation. *J. Muscle Res. Cell Motil.* **12**(2):171-182 (1991).

431 15. Stienen, G.J. Pathomechanisms in heart failure: the contractile connection. *J.*
432 *Muscle Res. Cell Motil.* **36**(1), 47-60 (2015).

433 16. Røe, Å.T., Aronsen, J.M., Skårdal, K., Hamdani, N., Linke, W.A., Danielsen, H.E.,
434 Sejersted, O.M., Sjaastad, I., & Louch, W.E. Increased passive stiffness promotes
435 diastolic dysfunction despite improved Ca^{2+} handling during left ventricular
436 concentric hypertrophy. *Cardiovasc. Res.* **113**(10), 1161-1172 (2017).

437 17. Edman, K.A.P., & Caputo, C. Release of calcium into the myofibrillar space in
438 response to active shortening of striated muscle. *Acta. Physiol.* **221**(2), 142-148
439 (2017).

440 18. Gomes, H.L., Menezes, T.N., Malacarne, P.F., Roman-Campos, D., Gondim, A.N.,
441 Cruz, J.S., Vassallo, D.V., & Figueiredo, S.G. Cardiovascular effects of Sp-CTX, a
442 cytolysin from the scorpionfish (*Scorpaenaplumieri*) venom. *Toxicon.* **118**, 141-148
443 (2016).

444 19. Wang, Q., Zhang, H., Wang, B., Wang, C., Xiao, L., & Zhang, L. β adrenergic
445 receptor/cAMP/PKA signaling contributes to the intracellular Ca^{2+} release by tentacle
446 extract from the jellyfish *Cyanea capillata*. *BMC Pharmacol. Toxicol.* **18**(1), 60
447 (2017).

448 20. Shen, Z.D., Yang, X.G., Azure, J.A., Bell, A.C., Sun, Y.Y., Cheng, X.Y., Dhlamini,
449 F.M., Gao, L.F., & Wang, Y. The urothelium enhance polarization in CFTX-1

- 450 peptide intervened toad urinary bladder. **18**(28), 695-701 (2019).
- 451 21. Ponce, D., Brinkman, D.L., Luna-Ramírez, K., Wright, C.E., & Dorantes-Aranda,
452 J.J. Comparative study of the toxic effects of *Chrysaora quinquecirrha* (Cnidaria:
453 Scyphozoa) and *Chironex fleckeri* (Cnidaria: Cubozoa) venoms using cell-based
454 assays. *Toxicon*. **106**, 57-67 (2015).
- 455 22. Brinkman, D.L., Konstantakopoulos, N., McInerney, B.V., Mulvenna, J., Seymour,
456 J.E., Isbister, G.K., & Hodgson, W.C. *Chironex fleckeri* (box jellyfish) venom proteins:
457 expansion of a cnidarian toxin family that elicits variable cytolytic and cardiovascular
458 effects. *J. Biol. Chem.* **289**(8), 4798-4812 (2014).
- 459 23. Andreosso, A., Bansal, P.S., Smout, M.J., Wilson, D., Seymour, J.E., & Daly, N.L.
460 Structural characterisation of predicted helical regions in the *Chironex fleckeri*
461 CfTX-1 toxin. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md16060201> (2018).
- 462 24. Stubbs, P.W., Walsh, L.D., D'Souza, A., Héroux, M.E., Bolsterlee, B., Gandevia,
463 S.C., & Herbert, R.D. History-dependence of muscle slack length following
464 contraction and stretch in the human vastuslateralis. *J. Physiol.* **596**(11), 2121-2129
465 (2018).
- 466 25. Wu, P.L., Chiu, C.R., Huang, W.N., & Wu, W.G. The role of sulfatide lipid
467 domains in the membrane pore-forming activity of cobra cardiotoxin. *Biochim.*
468 *Biophys. Acta.* **1818**(5), 1378-1385 (2012).
- 469 26. Abbott, B.C., & Aubert, X.M. The force exerted by active striated muscle during
470 and after change of length. *J. Physiol.* **117**, 77–86 (1952).
- 471 27. Hill, A.V., & Howarth, J.V. The reversal of chemical reactions in contracting
472 muscle during an applied stretch. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. B.* **151**, 169–193 (1959).
- 473 28. Sugi, H. Tension changes during and after stretch in frog muscle fibres. *J. Physiol.*
474 **225**(1), 237–253 (1972).
- 475 29. Herzog, W., & Leonard, T.R. Force enhancement following stretching of skeletal
476 muscle: a new mechanism. *J. Exp. Biol.* **205**, 1275-1283 (2002).
- 477 30. Herzog, W., Lee, E.J., & Rassier, D.E. Residual force enhancement in skeletal
478 muscle. *J. Physiol.* **574**, 635-642 (2006).
- 479 31. Edman, K.A.P., & Tsuchiya, T. Strain of passive elements during force

480 enhancement by stretch in frog muscle fibres. *J. Physiol.* **490**, 191–205 (1996).

481 32. Hisey B, Leonard TR, Herzog W. Does residual force enhancement increase with
482 increasing stretch magnitudes? *J. Biomech.* **42**(10), 1488-1492 (2009).

483 33. Gibbs, C.L., & Gibson, W.R. Effect of alterations in the stimulus rate upon energy
484 output, tension development and tension-time integral of cardiac muscle in rabbits.
485 *Circ. Res.* **27**(4), 611-618 (1970).

486 34. Harikumar, G., Egberongbe, Y., Nadel, S., heatley, E., Moxham, J., Greenough, A.,
487 & Rafferty, G.F. Tension-time index as a predictor of extubation outcome in ventilated
488 children. *Am. J. Respir. Crit. Care Med.* **180**(10), 982-988 (2009).

489 35. Horiuti, K. Some properties of the contractile system and sarcoplasmic reticulum
490 of skinned slow fibres from *Xenopus* muscle. *J. Physiol.* **373**, 1–23 (1986).

491 36. Sewanan, L.R., Moore, J.R., Lehman, W., & Campbell, S.G. Predicting Effects of
492 Tropomyosin Mutations on Cardiac Muscle Contraction through Myofilament
493 Modeling. *Front Physiol.* **7**, 473 (2016).

494 37. Suga, H., Goto, Y., Nozawa, T., Yasumura, Y., Futaki, S., & Tanaka, N. Force-time
495 integral decreases with ejection despite constant oxygen consumption and
496 pressure-volume area in dog left ventricle. *Circ. Res.* **60**(6), 797-803 (1987).

497 38. Alpert, N.R., Blanchard, E.M., & Mulieri, L.A. Tension-independent heat in rabbit
498 papillary muscle. *J. Physiol.* **414**, 433-453 (1989).

499 39. Baudouin, S.V., & Bateman, N.T. Contractility of papillary muscle from rats
500 exposed to 28 days of hypoxia, hypercapnia, and hypoxia with hypercapnia. *Thorax.*
501 **44**(10), 808–811 (1989).

502 40. Gabriel, D.A., Basford, J.R., & An, K.N. The reversal of antagonists facilitates the
503 peak rate of tension development. *Arch. Phys. Med. Rehabil.* **82**(3), 342-346 (2001).

504 41. Tamiya, K., Kikkawa, S., Gunji, A., Hori, M., & Sakurai, Y. Maximum rate of
505 tension fall during isometric relaxation at end-systolic fiber length in canine papillary
506 muscle. *Circ. Res.* **40**(6), 584-589 (1977).

507

508 **Figure and legend**

509

510 **The passive tension and subsequent force enhancement properties in cardiac papillary muscle**

511

Preload	Stretch mode	preparation	Solution	Stretch	PT _{max} (mg)	A _{IFE} (mg)	t ₁ (msec)	t ₂ (msec)	increased % of t ₂
High	Dual	Intact muscle	<i>Ringer's solution</i>	1 st	4488.10±612.70	1091.71±491.25	75.08±8.31 ^a	/	/
				2 nd	4576.96±435.80 ^a	6327.49±524.52 ^{***a}	/	117.42±34.80 ^{***a}	56
			3% <i>CaCl</i> ₂ - modified <i>Ringer's</i> solution	1 st	1779.10±569.45	687.37±43.20 ^{b1}	90.10±4.31	/	/
				2 nd	1132.13±98.25 ^{b2}	2062.10±287.59 ^{***b1,2}	/	105.11±8.51	16
			<i>Nifedipine</i> in <i>Ringer's</i> solution	1 st	1243.32±297.88	597.37±25.37	65.70±7.22	/	/
				2 nd	1779.66±157.71	909.75±11.91	/	79.64±6.17	22
		0.9% <i>saline</i> solution	1 st	1152.35±76.49	28.78±4.52 ^d	61.86±3.36 ^d	/	/	
			2 nd	1399.00±11.85	950.18±51.40 ^{***d}	/	103.48±8.80 ^{***d}	69	
		Shed muscle	<i>CfTX-1</i> in <i>Ringer's</i> solution	1 st	1066.49±101.33	1150.60±90.12 ^e	190.29±23.10 ^e	/	/
				2 nd	1868.87±119.59	1121.76±320.25 ^{***e}	/	260.20±34.50 ^{***e}	37

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517 **Figure 1.** Illustration of the excessive load in late diastole and relative muscle
518 relaxation velocity in cardiac ventricle

519 A. Left ventricle pressure (solid curve) and left atrial pressure (dotted curve) in
520 ventricular diastolic phase. The marked ① and ② represent the rising atrial
521 systolic pressure (kick from atrium), * was the maximum of atrial systolic
522 pressure. ② was the equilibrium point of atrial pressure to the moment
523 ventricular pressure. The ventricle was significantly contracted after the
524 equilibrium point ②. Symbol **P** indicated the kick amplitude (excessive load
525 amplitude) in ventricle late diastole phase.

526 B. The ventricle muscle relaxation velocity in each diastole and systole cycle. **a** and **b**
527 was the relaxation velocity response to ① and ②. The ventricular muscle
528 velocity was significantly reduced because of excessive load from the kick
529 (comparing with **a'** and **b'** in primary diastolic phase). The duration between **a** and
530 **b** indicated the kick time (excessive load time) in ventricle late diastole phase.

531 The images originated from Leite-Moreira A.F.^[8] and was modified by Dr. Yang
532 Wang.

533

534 **Figure 2.** Schematic of cardiac papillary muscle stretch processes *in vitro*

535 The sketched schematic of stretching cardiac papillary muscle. The muscle
536 preparations were primary lengthened to obtain a 1 g initial preload and stable for
537 5min (lengthening ① in y-axis). The muscle was further slowly lengthened to 20%
538 of its initial preload (lengthening ② in y-axis), defined as the low preload condition.

539 A single rapid active stretch was operated under low preload. After the low preload
540 testing, the muscle was further slowly lengthened to 40% of the low preload
541 (lengthening ③ in y-axis), defined as the high preload condition. The muscle was
542 rapidly active stretched twice under high preload condition (dual stretch mode).

543 The muscle preparations tolerated the sustained static stretch after each active stretch.

544 Myogenic spontaneous contraction and EF generated during tolerance.

545

546 **Figure 3.** The active stretch passive tension peak and EF in sustained static stretch

547 A. Under the low preload condition, the rapid active stretch induced a peak of
548 passive tension (symbol *), then generated a subsequent spontaneous contraction
549 during sustained static stretch. The force enhanced during relaxation. On the time

550 scale, phase **I** was the rising phase of the passive tension that rapidly reached to
551 the maximum (PT_{max}); the rising phase was further separated into two steps, a
552 slow rise and a rapid rising step (marked with **1** and **2**). Phase **II** was the
553 attenuation of passive tension during relaxation. The muscle tolerated sustained
554 static stretch in this phase, generated spontaneous contraction and EF waveform.
555 The peak of force enhancement was marked with 3 and the duration was marked
556 with **t**. The extension period after the EF was marked with 4. The EF amplitude
557 (A_{IFE}) normally did not surpass its PT_{max} .

558 **B.** Under the high preload condition, the muscle was operated by twice active
559 stretches (dual stretch testing mode). Muscle tolerated twice differed sustained
560 static stretch (after 1st and 2nd active stretch), therefore presented differed FE
561 waveform. In 2nd stretch, A_{IFE} normally surpassed its PT_{max} , and the 2nd FE
562 duration (t_2) prolonged than 1st FE duration (t_1).

563

564 **Figure 4.** Ca^{2+} influenced EF under the high preload condition

565 **A, B** and **C** waveforms recorded from the intact muscle, while **D** waveform was from
566 the CfTX-1 peptide shed muscle.

567 **A.** In 3% $CaCl_2$ -modified *Ringer's* solution, 2nd A_{IFE} dramatically increased, and
568 significantly surpassed its PT_{max} (182% of its PT_{max}). t_2 was 116% prolonged
569 than t_1 .

570 **B.** *Nifedipine* significantly reduced 2nd A_{IFE} and without surpassing its PT_{max} , t_2 was
571 not significantly longer than t_1 .

572 **C.** In the 0.9% *saline* solution, 2nd A_{IFE} were reduced and without surpass its PT_{max} .
573 However, t_2 were 167% prolonged than t_1 .

574 **D.** In shed muscle with *Ringer's* solution, 2nd A_{IFE} were reduced and without
575 surpassed its PT_{max} . t_2 significantly prolonged than its t_1 , both were prolonged
576 than that in intact muscle.

577

578 **Figure 5.** The force enhancement TTI_{max} and dT/dt_{max} under the high preload
579 condition

580 **A.** The maximum tension–time integral of the force enhancement (TTI_{max}) in different
581 solutions. In intact muscle, 2nd TTI_{max} was significantly increased in *Ringer's* solution
582 compared to the 1st TTI_{max} . However, 2nd TTI_{max} significantly increased after
583 *Nifedipine* intervention. However, the shed muscle 2nd TTI_{max} was not significant

584 increase (***) means $p < 0.001$).
585 B. Summary of the 1st and 2nd active stretch-induced maximum rate of the force
586 enhancement increase (dT/dt_{max}) in different solutions. In intact muscle, 2nd dT/dt_{max}
587 was not significant increase to its 1st dT/dt_{max} in *Ringer's* solution (dot line bar),
588 however a significant increasing observed in 3% CaCl₂ modified *Ringer's* solution
589 (solid line bar); *Nifedipine* intervention did not make significant increasing 2nd
590 dT/dt_{max} (solid line gey background bar). In shed muscle in *Ringer's* solution, 2nd
591 dT/dt_{max} were significantly increased, but not great increasing as that in the intact
592 muscle with 3% CaCl₂ modified *Ringer's* solution.

593

594 **Figure 6.** *CfTX-1* peptide from *Aurelia aurita* crude venom

595 A. The 43 kDa band in 10% acrylamide gel was the target band include the sequence
596 of *CfTX-1* peptide. Lane marked with SD was the molecular ruler; Lane marked
597 with cVN was separated proteins from *Aurelia aurita* crude venom. The sequence
598 of *IFNFFDLmKVK* was from the extract protein in 43 kDa band identified by
599 MALDI-TOF/TOF method and retrieval in Uniprot database (A7L035).

600 B. This sequence was further synthesized by commercial resin solid-phase method
601 and lyophilized and quality control analysed by HPLC and Electrospray Ionization
602 Tandem Mass Spectrometry (ESI-MS). The intensity peak value of 1027 at the
603 1400 Da molecular weight range represents the purified synthesized *CfTX-1*
604 peptide.

605

606

607

608

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

A. Low preloading

B. High preloading

Figure 4

A. 3% CaCl₂ modified Ringer's solution

B. Nifedipine (1.5mmol/L)

C. 0.9% NaCl

D. CfTX-1 peptide shed

Figure 5

A.

B.

Figure 6

